

Supplementary Figure 7. Transcript analysis of PICs differentiated into the 3 germ layers *in vitro*. (A-C) qRT-PCR analysis of the fold change increase in endothelial (A), hepatic (B) and neuronal (C) transcripts of differentiated C9 PICs, compared to undifferentiated PICs. (D) qRT-PCR analysis of myogenic, cardiomyogenic, endothelial, hepatic, and neuronal transcripts of undifferentiated C9 PICs. Bars represent the mean relative expression normalised to GAPDH. Error bars represent the standard deviation of the mean, n=3.